

OntoFoCE and ObE Forensics. Email-traceability supporting tools for Digital Forensics

Parra, H., Vegetti, M.

Supplementary material: SURVEY OF EVIDENCE ITEMS SUBJECT TO EXPERT EXAMINATION

This section contains all the supplementary information referring to the “evidence items subject to expert examination” (EISTEEs), including both the survey form implemented in the search for the judicial requirements and the analysis and tables with the results obtained after processing the information collected. All this is done to generate the competency questions OntoFoCE must answer. Below is the form used for the SURVEY ON THE EXPERT ANALYSIS OF EMAILS (Figure 1):

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RELEVAMIENTO DE INFORMACIÓN SOBRE PERICIAS DE CORREOS ELECTRÓNICOS

Estimado/a:

En la Facultad de Ingeniería de la UCASAL, estamos trabajando en la formulación de una ONTOLOGÍA PARA EL ANÁLISIS FORENSE DE CORREOS ELECTRÓNICOS. En el marco de ese proyecto, estamos abocados a obtener información sobre **pericias de correos electrónicos**.

Específicamente nos interesa conocer los **puntos de pericia** solicitados al respecto, entendiendo por tal “... *los requerimientos técnicos realizados por el juez respecto de un correo electrónico aportado como prueba digital en una causa y que determinan la tarea que tiene el Perito Informático en su rol de auxiliar de la justicia...*”.

El objetivo de este requerimiento es obtener información que permita conformar un conjunto de **datos básicos** que habitualmente permiten responder los puntos de pericia.

En particular, y en caso en que Ud. haya participado como perito informático en causas en donde **la prueba digital fue un CORREO ELECTRÓNICO**, le solicitamos conteste los siguientes ítems:

- 1) Indique los puntos de pericia **SIN MENCIÓN DE NINGUNA PALABRA, FRASE O CONSIDERACIÓN que pudiera identificar a la causa, personas o juzgados** intervinientes en la acción judicial.

Su colaboración será valiosa para la investigación.

Muchas gracias!

MBA Ing. H. Beatriz P. de Gallo
Docente e Investigadora
Facultad de Ingeniería
UCASAL
www.ucasal.edu.ar

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Figure 1: Survey of EISTEEs of emails

This survey of expert users helped us identify 86 initial EISTEEs on emails, which are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: EISTEEs surveyed.

N°	EISTEEs surveyed
01	Who is the holder of the box sss@yahoo.com.ar, When was it enabled? indicate if in the period of the case was the contact system of the plaintiff with the defendant or his email boxes; persona1@dominio.com.ar, usuario@yahoo.com.ar, persona2@dominio.com.ar, persona3@dominio.com.ar and persona4@dominio.com.ar and print or transcribe the emails received and issued from that service tray between the following subjects and date.
02	A fs. 33 vta. is requested: "analyze and rule if there are records of authenticity, veracity and plausibility of the senders and accounts, date, time and content of the e-mails addressed to XXX, which are detailed in the lawsuit and which are attached forms for comparison."
03	A fs. 34 requested: "Identify which were the source and destination computers of the message. In addition, it must collect useful data to determine the content of the e-mail in question. The servers or Internet providers – which operate as a link between the sender and the recipient of the e-mail – have information inherent to the date on which the e-mail was sent or forwarded, connection duration, attachments, identification number of the equipment of origin and destination of the communications – traffic data.
04	A fs. 42 is requested: "... to be constituted at the defendant's domicile and to extract a copy of the information from the hard disk or computer database where the emails corresponding to the XXX and ZZZ accounts in Argentina are filed; copy of the personal account of the Email CCC@empresa.com.ar of XXX during the period 2007/2009.
05	Access the computer and extract any information from which emails in which the "xxxxxxx@xxxx.com.ar" box appears as sender or recipient may arise
06	As ordered in the present proceedings, in fs. 47 and that considering the computer records existing in the branch of the defendant entity and the evidence added in the file, detail the procedures carried out in the name of the subscriber from 24/05/2011 to 15/06/2011. All other data of interest for a total clarification of the facts.
07	In accordance with the provisions of the present proceedings, the authenticity of the emails reserved in the file must be verified. In relation to them, determine if they are authentic and belong to their owners.
08	Add to the report the emails sent and received from those accounts between their creation and YEAR MONTH inclusive
09	Analyzing the respondent's server, verify the current or past existence of the user or account xx@xx and indicate the date of creation
10	Certify or inform that the e-mail outlined above are true and sent by the customer service of the firm XXX.
11	Check the authenticity of the emails that are reserved in cars. In relation to them, determine if they are authentic and belong to their owners.
12	Check the existence, date, and content thereof in the DOMAIN account
13	From the analysis of all the equipment of the personnel of the opposite, determine the veracity or not of the emails that my part attributes to the employer.
14	Determine the physical place of origin of extracted emails
15	Determine the source and destination server involved in communication between mailboxes xx@empresa.com.ar and ff@empresa2.com.ar
16	Determine the authenticity of the printing of the website and an email attached to these proceedings.
17	Determine the authenticity of the printing of an email attached to these actions in fjs. 48.
18	Determine the authenticity of an email attached to these proceedings
19	Determine the existence of the xxxxxxxx domain and the e-mail box that arises from it
20	Determine the existence and veracity of sending and receiving the mails detailed in these works.
21	Determine the veracity of the emails sent and received by Mr. XX with the defendant company. And any other information that it considers of interest in the cause.
22	Determine the veracity of emails sent and received by Mr. XX with the defendant company

N°	EISTEEs surveyed
23	Determine the veracity of the email
24	Determine whether the email attached as evidence was modified or altered and if so, whether the tampering was done from the hijacked computer.
25	Determine whether the emails attached as evidence are on the defendant's computer equipment.
26	Determine whether emails sent from a validated server, such as those used here by parties, x@x.com or y@y.com or z@z.com can be detected from their source and destination.
27	Determine the origin, authenticity, and timeline of each of those messages.
28	Determine the existence of individualized mailboxes in the embedded documentary.
29	Determine if the following attachments were sent from the x@x.com mobile device to email y@y.com on the x/x/xxxx day: a, b, c
30	Dictate if there are records of authenticity, veracity and plausibility of the senders and accounts, date, time, and content of the e-mails addressed to USER
31	The expert shall indicate whether it is possible that messages sent or received, such as the accompanying texts contained therein, may have been altered in their dates and times of issue or receipt.
32	In case of ignorance of 4 Emails received by the taxpayer plaintiff, computer expertise is practiced in the email: usuario@dominio.com
33	In case of ignorance of the veracity of the emails, I request that a computer expert be appointed to determine if they were sent by the actor or by his father or brother, in their email accounts.
34	In case of ignorance, a computer expert is appointed in order to verify the existence, date, and content thereof in the Gmail account.
35	In case of refusal of all emails offered as evidence, I request that a computer expertise be carried out in order to inform if the emails received and sent belong to the Company and / or persons sued herein.
36	In the presence of the holders of the email accounts involved, who must provide the corresponding passwords, inform if such emails were issued and received from and by the email addresses consigned in such documentation.
37	Extract any email containing one or more data contained in the following list: Name: XX, DNI: XXX, Phone: XXXX, Address: XXXXX.
38	Identify the date and time of receipt of emails
39	Identify the IP of origin of the emails
40	Identify the email addresses of the sender and receiver of such emails
41	Identify which were the source and destination computers of the message. In addition, it must collect useful data to determine the content of the e-mail in question. The servers or Internet providers – which operate as a link between the sender and the recipient of the e-mail – have information inherent to the date on which the e-mail was sent or forwarded, connection duration, attachments, identification number of the equipment of origin and destination of the communications – traffic data.
42	Indicate whether the mail attached as evidence was forwarded to more than one recipient and who they were.
43	Indicate whether it is possible that messages sent or received, such as the attached texts contained therein, may have been altered in their dates and times of issuance or receipt
44	Indicate which domain the emails came from
45	Indicate the IP where the emails came from.
46	Indicate the creation date
47	Indicate the location of the sending IP of the certificates offered.
48	Indicate the dates on which the aforementioned emails were sent and received.
49	Indicate if communication between x@x.com mail and any ZZZZ account or person was common and frequent.
50	Indicate if you can determine the authenticity of the accompanied emails as proof of my client's right to the cause.
51	Report if any of the messages sent had as "subject" topics related to YYYYY.
52	Inform if during the contractual relationship and even after the end of the contractual relationship, the parties sent emails from the x@x.com address to the xx and zz accounts.
53	Report whether emails sent from xx and/or zz were received in the x@x.com account
54	Report whether emails exchanged by the parties may be subject to adulteration

N°	EISTEEs surveyed
55	Report if the emails received and sent belong to the Company and/or persons hereafter
56	Inform if communication with customers by email is common
57	Report whether such e-mails were issued and received from and by the e-mail addresses provided
58	Enter the email account of the plaintiff, investigate, analyze and determine the validity and authenticity of the sending by the company EMPRESA S.A. and / or COMERCIO of emails containing the contractual proposal. Certify the validity of printed emails that are accompanied as proof.
59	Tell if you can tell if any of these messages had any attachments with any related content.
60	In the case of ignorance of proof of mails, a computer expert is appointed in order to determine the date of issuance and veracity of the emails that were questioned.
61	Proceed to the digital copying of the emails that contain the information related to the cause in a removable storage medium, becoming a depository of the same and guaranteeing the minimum steps foreseen by the forensic computer (acquisition, preservation, obtaining and presentation).
62	The authenticity of the exchange by e-mail must be verified
63	Determine the IP number where the emails came from.
64	It is issued on whether the email account is usuario@dominio.com used by Mr. USER and indicate if said account belongs to any of the defendant firms (SIGNATURE1 and / or SIGNATURE2),
65	Computer expertise is provided so that the expert of the analysis of all the equipment of the personnel of the opposite, determines the veracity or not of the emails that my part attributes to the employer.
66	V.S. is requested to remove expert computer engineer from the list who, having in view the emails, determines the authenticity of the same, port of entry and exit and any other data of interest.
67	It is verified and verified from which domain the emails came
68	The authenticity of the accompanying documentation is verified and verified, with expert requisition on page 62 to page 107 of the main body of the aforementioned files.
69	The authenticity of the accompanying documentation is verified and verified.
70	If from the records of the same it appears that the account xx@xx and yy@yy.com, was deleted in your case indicate date.
71	If those emails were maintained between the e-mail account of Mr. USER1 and the usuario@dominio.com account belonging to Mr. USER2.
72	If these e-mails have been sent from the addresses indicated therein and if they have been sent to the addresses indicated therein.
73	If the content of these emails is consistent with the content of the emails accompanied in the documentary.
74	If, based on the above considerations, you can rule whether the emails exchanged by the parties and attached in paper format are authentic.
75	Whether they were received at the recipient or not
76	If you have detected any signs of tampering in them
77	If the "Attached Texts" coincide with the documentation accompanied by me in the previous point
78	If the e-mails that are attached printed to the present application, correspond to the email account usuario@dominio.com belonging to Mr. NAME SURNAME, task for which this party offers to make available access to the referred email account
79	If emails are documented on servers
80	If the emails that appear there as sent or received are of the dates indicated by my party in your lawsuit and if they coincide with those mentioned in b.18 (Plaintiff's Evidence) which are detailed as About folder of emails and attachments of the plaintiff's mail xx@yahoo.com.ar (it is mentioned in the lawsuit and consists of 71 pages)
81	If the e-mails exchanged that are attached on paper to the file coincide with those actually sent and received electronically
82	Additionally, and for the hypothetical case of ignorance of 4 Emails received by the taxpayer plaintiff, computer expertise is practiced in the email: yo_estudio@hotmail.com.

N°	EISTEEs surveyed
83	Having in view the emails determine the authenticity of the same, port of entry and exit and all other data of interest.
84	Verify the authenticity of extracted emails.
85	Verify the emails were sent between FATHER (padre@live.com), person (persona@hotmail.com) and SON hijo@hotmail.com .
86	And if the texts that are reserved in Secretariat correspond to those sent by the respective servers

With these results, a meeting was held under the dynamics of Focus Group with the participation of the researchers of the Digital Forensics Group of the UCASAL, who also act as experts, in order to reduce the 86 points to an adequate number considering that many of those points of expertise initially surveyed expressed the same, but with different words. Thus, 46 points of expertise were obtained as indicated below (Table 2).

Table 2: Resulting EISTEEs

N°	EISTEEs
1)	Who is the salta@yahoo.com.ar box holder? , When was it enabled? if in the period of the case was the plaintiff's contact system with the defendant or their email boxes; persona1@dominio.com.ar , usuario@yahoo.com.ar , persona2@dominio.com.ar , persona3@dominio.com.ar and persona4@dominio.com.ar and print or transcribe the emails received and issued from that service tray between those subjects and date.
2)	Access the computer and extract any information from which emails in which the " xxxxxxx@xxxx.com.ar " box appears as sender or recipient may arise.
3)	Add to the report the emails sent and received from those accounts between their creation and YEAR MONTH inclusive.
4)	Check the existence, date, and content of the emails in the domain account "dominio.com".
5)	Determine the physical place of origin of extracted emails.
6)	Determine the source and destination server involved in communication between mailboxes usuario@empresa.com.ar and usuario@empresa2.com.ar .
7)	Determine the existence and veracity of sending and receiving the mails detailed in these works.
8)	Determine the veracity of emails sent and received by Mr. XX with the defendant company.
9)	Determine if the attached email was modified or altered and if so, if the tampering was done from the hijacked computer.
10)	Determine whether the emails attached as evidence are on the defendant's computer equipment.
11)	Determine the origin, authenticity, and timeline of each of those messages.
12)	Determine the existence of individualized mailboxes in the embedded documentary.
13)	Determine if the following attachments were sent from the mobile device (from the account) x@x.com to the email y@y.com the following attachments on the x/x/xxxx day.
14)	Dictate if there are records of authenticity, veracity and plausibility of the senders and accounts, date, time and content of the e-mails addressed to USER.
15)	In case of ignorance of 4 Emails received by the taxpayer plaintiff, computer expertise is practiced in the email: usuario@dominio.com .
16)	In case of ignorance of the veracity of the emails, I request that a computer expert be appointed to determine if they were sent by the actor or by his father or brother, in their email accounts.
17)	Extract any email containing one or more data contained in the following list: Name: XX, DNI: XXX, Phone: XXXX, Address: XXXXX.
18)	Identify which were the source and destination computers of the message. In addition, it must collect useful data to determine the content of the e-mail in question. The servers or Internet providers – which operate as a link between the sender and the recipient of the e-mail – have information inherent to the date on which the e-mail was sent or forwarded, connection duration, attachments, identification number of the equipment of origin and destination of the communications – traffic data.
19)	Indicate whether the mail attached as evidence was forwarded to more than one recipient and who they were.
20)	Indicate which domain the emails came from.

N°	EISTEEs
21)	Indicate the IP where the emails came from.
22)	Indicate the location of the sending IP of the certificates offered.
23)	Indicate the dates on which the aforementioned emails were sent and received.
24)	Indicate if communication between email x@x.com with any ZZZZ account or person was common and frequent.
25)	Please report if any of the messages sent had as "subject" topics related to YYYYYYYYYY.
26)	Inform if during the contractual relationship and even after it ended, the parties sent emails from the x@x.com address to the xx and zz accounts.
27)	Report whether emails sent from xx and/or zz were received in the x@x.com account.
28)	Report whether emails exchanged by the parties may be subject to adulteration.
29)	Report whether such e-mails were sent to and received from and by the e-mail addresses listed.
30)	Enter the email account of the plaintiff, investigate, analyze, and determine the validity and authenticity of the sending by the company EMPRESA S.A. and / or COMERCIO of emails containing the contractual proposal. Certify the validity of printed emails that are accompanied as proof.
31)	Tell if you can tell if any of these messages had attachments with any related content.
32)	In the case of ignorance of proof of mails, a computer expert is appointed in order to determine the date of issuance and veracity of the emails that were questioned.
33)	Determine the IP number where the emails came from.
34)	It is issued on whether the email account is usuario@dominio.com used by Mr. USER and indicate if said account belongs to any of the defendant firms (SIGNATURE1 and / or SIGNATURE2).
35)	Whether (the emails) were received at the recipient or not.
36)	If such emails were kept between the email account of Mr. USER1 and the usuario@dominio.com account belonging to Mr. USER2.
37)	If those e-mails were sent from the addresses listed therein and if they were sent to the addresses indicated therein.
38)	If the content of these emails is consistent with the content of the emails accompanied in the documentary.
39)	If, based on the above considerations, you can rule whether the emails exchanged by the parties and attached in paper format are authentic.
40)	If the e-mails that are attached printed to the present application, correspond to the email account usuario@dominio.com belonging to Mr. NAME SURNAME, task for which this party offers to make available access to the referred email account.
41)	If the emails that appear there as sent or received are of the dates indicated by my party in your complaint and if they coincide with those mentioned in b.18 (Plaintiff's Test) which are detailed as About folder of emails and attachments of the plaintiff's mail usuario@dominio.com.ar .
42)	If the e-mails exchanged that are attached on paper to the file coincide with those actually sent and received electronically.
43)	Having in view the emails determine the authenticity of the same, port of entry and exit and all other data of interest.
44)	Verify the authenticity of extracted emails.
45)	Check the emails that were sent between FATHER (padre@dominio.com), person (persona@dominio.com) and SON hijo@dominio.com .
46)	And if the texts that are reserved in Secretariat correspond to those sent by the respective servers.

These 46 points of expertise were taken as requirements for the construction of OntoFoCE, and 21 competency questions were defined to answer them.

Then a cross was made between both sets (points of expertise and questions of competence) in order to verify that each point of expertise identified, has one or more associated competence questions that answer it, this is shown in Table II-3. In which successive rows indicate the points of expertise, the columns indicate the competency questions that the ontology can answer, and the intersection of each row/column that has been shaded indicates which competency questions answer the skill point.

